

Special Relativity, Legendre Transformations and Fluctuations

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Momentum and velocity are two well-known physical observables in classical physics (and quantum physics as well because quantum particles have impulse and move through space in a certain amount of time based on an external clock and ruler). They are, however, measured in different ways. Velocity describes motion through x in some time t , while p is measured through impulses. Thus one does not need a clock to measure momentum. It may be measured in terms of the damage done to a foil, compression of a spring etc. Thus $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ etc., i.e. a numerical number associated with momentum does not automatically yield the velocity unless one knows rest mass. In many situations rest mass is known (i.e. one deals with an electron etc) and so there seems to be a tendency to consider momentum and velocity to be almost the same thing when they are distinctly different.

In fact, we argue that the notion of wavefunction $W(x)$ and density $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ are associated with momentum and velocity respectively. In fact, for a free particle these two measurables are linked with completely different spatial probabilities. Constant velocity implies $P(x)=\text{constant}$ while $\exp(ipx)$ describes the two-dimensional x -probability associated with p which is based on a constant m_0 and v .

In special relativity for a free particle (i.e. p constant, v constant), there are two well known Lorentz invariants: $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$ ($c=1$) and $A = -Et + px$. One may note that v does not appear explicitly even though one may write E and p in terms of v i.e. $E = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$ and $p=Ev$. The first invariant describes E in terms of rest mass and p (measured through impulse). The second involves p, E and x, t with x and t appearing as independent even though ultimately $x(t)$ and $v=dx/dt=\text{constant} = x/t$ if x and t both start at 0. This independence is crucial because it means one may consider fluctuations which keep A constant separately. For example, if $t \rightarrow t + \hbar/E$ and $x \rightarrow x + \hbar/p$, then A remains constant. This leads to the idea of the quantum wavelength and a spatial probability independent of t , namely $\exp(ipx)$. One average, however, $x=vt$, but how does this appear in Lorentz invariants? There is no explicit v .

We argue that the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ must convert E from a function of p to one in v and that this occurs through a Legendre transformation. Thus the form of the invariant is itself a Legendre transformation with E being transformed into L , the Lagrangian. There is, however, a second important feature because $p=dL/dv$ (partial) and given that p is constant, $dp/dt=0$ so $d/dt dL/dv \text{ partial} =0$ which is in the form of an extremization. We argue that this is not an accident. $dL/dv=p$ follows from E being constant, so, in other words, it follows from the px term. This same term leads to $\exp(ipx)$ which means that one does not have smooth $x=vt$ motion within a wavelength. Thus, we argue that when one transforms to the second measurable v , the notion of this fluctuation behaviour must also be manifested. In other words, $v=\text{constant}$ or dv/dt is not enough. The extremization behaviour of the Lagrangian, we argue, is thus not a mathematical convenience, but gives an indication that even though the extreme path $x=vt$ is followed on average, other paths are sampled. We argue that this idea is incorporated into special relativity, in fact within a single Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$.

Momentum and Velocity Measurables

In nonrelativistic classical mechanics, it is easy to consider velocity and momentum as essentially the same thing, with momentum being multiplied by m_0 , rest mass. We argue, however, that quantum mechanics treats them in a dramatically separate manner. In particular, a constant velocity means $P(x)=\text{constant}$. A constant momentum, however, is associated with $\exp(ipx)$ which contains a wavelength \hbar/p . Nevertheless, the quantum particle with a wavelength (i.e. two spatial x-probabilities) moves on average as $x=vt$. One may note that $\exp(ipx)$ does not indicate the velocity value i.e. $p = m_1v_1 = m_2v_2 \dots$. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ seems to point to a different type of measurement than velocity.

We argue that momentum is measured through impulse (e.g. the damage it causes on striking a foil, compression of a spring etc). One does not need to measure x and t together and $p = m_1v_1 = m_2v_2 \dots$ all cause the same impulse. Velocity, on the other hand, depends on $x(t)$ i.e. one measures travel in time and space together. Thus momentum and velocity are measured in completely different manners, yet both, we argue, may be related to spatial probabilities.

As already noted, $P(x)=\text{constant}$ for $v=\text{constant}$, but momentum is linked with $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. We have argued in previous notes that this distribution retains the information of the force \rightarrow impulse which the particle may impart at any instant. (For example, a potential also is linked with its force.) The two distributions, however, are linked as $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = \text{constant} = P(x)$ as constant p and constant v exist for the same system.

We argue that these ideas have implications in special relativity.

Special Relativity of a Free Particle

Special relativity often deals with viewing a particle from different frames moving with constant velocities. Thus the Lorentz transformation matrix explicitly contains a velocity. The four-vectors in special relativity are (p,E) and (x,t) . Velocity is not part of a 4-vector. Yet, as argued in the above section, velocity and p are measurables (although measured in different ways) and so we argue that Lorentz invariants, even though written in terms of E,p, x,t must yield information about BOTH p and v . In particular, we argue that even though $E = m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$ and $p = Ev$ ($c=1$) for a free particle, the Lorentz invariants themselves must yield information directly about p and v .

Two key Lorentz invariants for a free particle are:

$$EE = pp + m_0m_0 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad A = -Et + px \quad ((1b))$$

((1a)) expresses $E(p)$ i.e. energy in terms of the measurable p . What about E in terms of the measurable v ? Mathematically (as seen in thermodynamics), one uses a Legendre transformation to write a function with switched variables. In this case, one wishes to change form $E(p)$ to a function in v , switching p and v . Thus $A = -Et + px$ must be in the form of a Legendre transformation. In other words, the unusual metric of special relativity accomplishes this goal. If x and t are measured from 0 then:

$$A/t = -E + pv \quad ((2))$$

((2)) is in the form of a Legendre transformation and one may call:

$$A/t = L(v) = \text{Lagrangian} = -E + pv \quad ((3))$$

Before proceeding, one may note that ((1b)) treats x and t in an independent fashion, while ((2)), the Legendre transformation, links them through $x/t=v$. With independence, ((1b)) yields:

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \quad \text{or} \quad -id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is linked to the measurable p or impulse. It suggests two spatial x -probabilities $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ in two dimensions. At the same time p is constant as is v .

If information about "fluctuations" is contained in $-Et+px$ for p , we argue that a similar type of physics should appear for v . In other words, one cannot argue for fluctuations in p according to $\exp(ipx)$ and then say $v=\text{constant}$, $dv/dt=0$ describe the full velocity picture, even though these hold on average. How does one show some kind of fluctuation associated with velocity?

We argue that $A=-Et+px$ or its Legendre velocity form ((3)) has a velocity fluctuation scheme built in. Given that E is constant:

$$dL/dv \text{ partial} = p \quad ((5))$$

We note that ((5)) follows from the term pv which is the same term " px " which yielded $\exp(ipx)$. Taking d/dt of ((5)) yields:

$$0 = dp/dt = d/dt dL/dv \text{ partial} \quad ((6))$$

((6)), however, is in the form of an extremization result. Thus one may vary:

$$\text{Integral } L \text{ dt} \quad \text{and use integration by parts i.e. } dL/dv \text{ delta } v \longrightarrow -d/dt dL/dv \text{ delta } x \quad ((7))$$

The extremization process shows that even though there is an extreme solution $v=\text{constant}$, different paths are considered in the Lagrangian extremization process. We thus argue that this consideration of different paths to obtain the extreme path is not simply a mathematical formulation, but is linked with the fluctuations of $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, p is a measurable which is constant, but is associated with x -probability. Velocity is another measurable which is also constant, but should be associated with similar x -probability behaviour in some fashion. We argue that the Lagrangian extremization process demonstrates this mechanism. Furthermore, both the $\exp(ipx)$ fluctuations associated with p and the Lagrangian extremization approach both follow from the same Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that p and v are two essential measurables in both classical and quantum physics, but each is measured differently. We argue that one should not think of momentum (nonrelativistically) as simply a constant multiplied by velocity. Rather it is linked with impulse which measures the damage done to a foil, effect on a spring etc. $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ etc. so a constant p does not immediately yield v (if one does not know m), but one may still measure it. Velocity, on the other hand, measures x travel through time.

Special relativity, even though based on v in the Lorentz transformation matrix, uses 4-vectors (p,E) and (x,t) . There is no velocity 4-vector. Thus, two common Lorentz invariants: $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ ($c=1$) and $A = -Et + px$ do not explicitly contain v . The latter, we argue, leads to $dA/dx = p$ which in turn leads to free particle quantum mechanics i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. Thus even though p is constant (and may be measured), there is a x -probability distribution (actually $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$). We argue that this is associated with the force-like nature of an impulse. Velocity, on the other hand, is constant and associated with $P(x) = \text{constant}$.

In this note, we stress that even though $P(x)=\text{constant}$ and $v=\text{constant}$, the fluctuation nature associated with p should also be associated with v . Furthermore, even though the two Lorentz invariants do not contain v explicitly, velocity is a measurable, and there should exist a Legendre transformation which changes $E(p)$ into a function of L . In particular, $A = -Et + px$ is this Legendre transformation (hence the unusual metric in special relativity). Thus $v=x/t$ and $A/t = -E + pv$ with $A/t = L(v) = \text{Lagrangian}$.

It is not simply the case that one Lorentz invariant is in the form of a Legendre transformation, a constant E implies that $dL/dv = p$. For a constant p , $dp/dt = d/dt dL/dv = 0$, so the px term, now pv , causes the Lagrangian to be associated with an extremization result. Thus, the extreme result is $v=\text{constant}$, but $\int L dt$ considers various different paths, i.e. there is fluctuation occurring just as in $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, $-Et + px$ describes quantum $\exp(ipx)$ fluctuations associated with the measurable p (impulse), but also provides the Legendre form to change to the measurable v and provides for its extremization which shows that physically more occurs than simply $v=\text{constant}$. In other words, we argue that the consideration of different paths in $\int L dt$ is an indication that one does not simply have smooth motion $x=vt$. Both Lagrangian extremization and quantum free particle fluctuations $\exp(ipx)$ follow from the same Lorentz invariant, but are associated with different measurables v and p .